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Phosphorus recovery from wastewater sludges by acid and alkaline leaching

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Tiivistelmä - Referat - Abstract <p>Fosfori (P) on uusiutumaton ja korvaamaton luonnonvara, joka on olennainen kaikelle elämälle maapallolla. Se on keskeisessä roolissa ruokajärjestelmien ylläpitämisessä ja toimii arvokkaana raaka-aineena teollisissa prosesseissa. Nykyisten P-varantojen arvioidaan ehtyvän seuraavan vuosisadan kuluessa, mikä on johtanut lainsäädännöllisiin toimiin kestävien vaihtoehtoisten lähteiden etsimiseksi. Yksi tällainen lähde on kunnallinen jätevedenpuhdistamon liete, johon fosfori saostetaan estämään vesistöjen rehevöitymistä. Kemiallinen liuotus on osoittautunut tehokkaaksi P:n liuottamisessa ja talteenotossa tuotteena, mutta tulokset ovat olleet epäjohdonmukaisia rautakäsittelyllä lietteillä.</p> <p>Tämä opinnäytetyö pyrkii selvittämään epäjohdonmukaisuuksien taustalla olevia syitä ja löytämään tehokkaan menetelmän P:n talteenottoon kemiallisen liuotuksen ja raudan pelkistyksen yhdistelmällä. Tutkimuksessa kokeiltiin liuotusta eri pH-tasoilla käyttäen neljää eri lietetyyppiä. Emäksinen menetelmä oli tehokkaampi fosfaatin liuottamisessa mädätyksen syöttölietteestä (53,8 %) ja lingotusta lietteestä (11,2 %), mikä johtuu todennäköisesti näiden lietteiden korkeammasta kuiva-aine- ja orgaanisen aineen pitoisuudesta ja suuremmasta orgaanisen P:n vapautumisesta verrattuna mädätettyyn lietteeseen. Happokäsittely oli puolestaan tehokkaampi mädätetylle lietteelle (39,4 %) ja lingotun lietteen nestefaasille (35,6 %), joissa on enemmän epäorgaanista materiaalia. Menetelmän ja olosuhteiden optimointi, kuten neste/kiintoaine -suhteen säätö, voisi edelleen parantaa lingotun lietteen liuotuspotentiaalia. Teoreettiseen struviitin tuotantoon mädätetty liete tai kuivattu liete ovat ihanteellisia korkean fosforin vapautumisen (pH 12 ja 2) ja merkittävän ammoniumpitoisuuden vuoksi. Tämä tutkimus auttaa valitsemaan sopivan P:n talteenottomenetelmän ja -olosuhteet eri lietemateriaaleille sekä tarkastelee syitä hapon ja emäksen käytön eroihin liuotuksessa. Nykyinen puutteellinen P:n, raudan ja rikin esiintymismuotojen ymmärrys estää P:n käyttäytymisen täydellisen ymmärtämisen jätevedenpuhdistusprosessissa sekä tehokkaiden talteenottostrategioiden kehittämisen.</p>		
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Tiivistelmä - Referat - Abstract Phosphorus (P) is a non-renewable and irreplaceable resource integral to all life on Earth. It plays a key role in upkeeping food systems and serves as a valuable raw material for industrial processes. Current P reserves are expected to be depleted within the next century, prompting increased legislative efforts to find sustainable alternative sources, such as the municipal wastewater sludge, where P is precipitated to prevent eutrophication in waterbodies. Wet-chemical leaching has proven effective in dissolving P and recovering it as a product, but the results are inconsistent in iron treated sludges. This thesis seeks to explore the reasons behind these inconsistencies and find an effective method for P recovery through chemical dissolution combined with iron reduction, by experimenting with leaching at different pH levels using four different sludge materials. Alkaline method was more effective in solubilizing phosphate from digester feed (53.8%) and dewatered sludge (11.2%), likely due to the higher dry weight and organic matter content of these sludges, as well as a greater release of organic phosphorus compared to digested sludge. Acid treatment was more effective for digested sludge (39.4%) and liquid from dewatering (35.6%), which have more inorganic material. Optimizing the leaching methodology and conditions, such as adjusting the liquid/solid ratio or employing sequential washing, could further enhance P leaching potential for dewatered sludge. For theoretical struvite production digested sludge or dewatered sludge are ideal due to their high P release at pH 12 and 2 and substantial ammonium concentrations. This study aids in selecting suitable P recovery methods and conditions for different sludge materials and examines the potential reasons for differences between acid and alkaline leaching. The current limited characterization of P, iron and sulphur prevents a complete understanding of P behaviour and fate in wastewater treatment plants, as well as the development of effective P recovery strategies.		
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Abbreviations

P	Phosphorus
EU	European Union
WWTP	Wastewater treatment plant
EBPR	Enhanced biological phosphorus removal
Ca	Calcium
Fe	Iron
Al	Aluminium
PO ₄ ³⁻	(Ortho)phosphate
Fe-P	Iron phosphate compounds, such as FePO ₄
SSA	Sewage sludge ash
AD	Anaerobic digestion
IP	Inorganic phosphorus
OP	Organic phosphorus
AP	Apatite-phosphorus (Calcium-bound phosphorus)
NAIP	Non-apatite phosphorus
L/S ratio	Liquid/solid ratio
OH ⁻	Hydroxide ion
Fe(OH) ₃	Iron hydroxides
HAP	Hydroxyapatite (Ca ₅ (PO ₄) ₃ (OH) + 3 H ₂ O)
SO ₄ ²⁻	Sulphate ion
S ²⁻	Sulphide
FeS	Iron sulphides
CaP	Calcium phosphates
MAP	Magnesium-ammonium-phosphate or Struvite (NH ₄ MgPO ₄ · 6 H ₂ O)

DF	Digester feed
Dig S	Digested sludge
DS	Dewatered sludge
DS liquid	Dewatered sludge liquid
DW	Dry weight
FS	Fixed solids
VS	Volatile solids
NH_4^+	Ammonium
Mg^{2+}	Magnesium

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Phosphorus (P) is a non-renewable and irreplaceable raw resource that is integral to all life on Earth. It is an essential nutrient that plays a key role in ensuring food security and is also a valuable raw material for various industrial processes (de Boer et al., 2019; Mayer et al., 2016). In 2018 around 82% or 39 Mt of mined phosphorus was used in agriculture as fertilizers, while the rest was used in animal feed production and industrial processes (Cordell et al., 2009; de-Bashan & Bashan, 2004; Food and Agriculture Organization, 2025). The demand for phosphorus fertilizers is expected to continue to grow due to increasing global populations, dietary changes and the rising share of biofuels (Wilfert et al., 2015). According to the International Water Management Institute, phosphorus production will grow by 70% by 2050 to satisfy the rapidly growing demand (Cieřlik & Konieczka, 2017). Cordell et al. (2009) have predicted that phosphorus production will peak around 2033, and the phosphorus reserves will be completely drained within the next 100 years. The uncertainty in world markets caused by recent conflicts has led to glaring sustainability and geopolitical challenges, as phosphorus mining is concentrated into only a handful of countries, causing concerns of self-sufficiency and equitable fertilizer access (de Boer et al., 2019; Egle et al., 2015).

Though the exact depletion date is still debated, the fact is that new sustainable development measures must be taken in the use and handling of phosphorus, otherwise it will eventually run out (Illakwahhi et al., 2024). The European Union (EU) has enlisted phosphorus as a critical resource, which has led to new regulations in many EU countries to recover phosphorus from alternative sustainable sources (Huygens et al., 2019; Regulation 2019/1009). One possible option for phosphorus recovery is the municipal wastewater.

Phosphorus enters wastewater mainly from feces and cleaning products (Berninger et al., 2017). Over the past decades the inefficient use of the global phosphorus resources has led to the loss of excess nutrients into waterbodies

and landfills, causing eutrophication and dead zones (Mayer et al., 2016). For this reason, phosphorus removal in wastewater treatment is highly regulated to prevent P release into the environment. So far, P removal has been done without any intended recovery or reuse. The price of mined phosphorus has been low enough to make recovery uneconomic (Mayer et al., 2016). Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are increasingly being considered as integral components of circular sustainability systems, through the integration of energy production and resource recovery into the clean water treatment process (Neczaj & Grosser, 2018). Globally approximately 3.0 Tg P/year is treated in municipal WWTPs (Melia et al., 2017; Qadir et al., 2020). Consequently, P recovery from sewage sludge as secondary raw materials or as phosphorus-rich fertilizers is currently one of the most researched solutions to tackle phosphorus depletion (Saoudi et al., 2023). Estimates suggest that in the EU approximately 17–31% of the phosphorus could be replaced with recycled nutrients derived from manure, municipal wastewater, and sludge by 2030 (Huygens et al., 2019).

As much as 98% of incoming phosphorus can be removed from incoming wastewater using either biological and/or chemical methods (Urho et al., 2022). In enhanced biological phosphorus removal (EBPR) phosphorus accumulating organisms are used to collect phosphorus as long-chain polymers in alternating aerobic and anaerobic processes (Amann et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2015). EBPR relies on the specific conditions favourable to the growth of certain microbial communities, which may limit its applicability in all wastewater treatment plants, such as the majority of those in Finland (Berninger et al., 2017). The more commonly applied method for phosphorus removal is chemical precipitation, which involves the use of di- or trivalent metal salts of iron (Fe), calcium (Ca), or aluminium (Al) to precipitate phosphorus into the sludge as metal phosphate compounds. Currently, phosphorus precipitation using iron-based coagulants is the most common method in Finland (Karttunen, 2004). Following chemical precipitation, phosphorus becomes concentrated in a solid sludge, which is not used, and is ultimately disposed with the sludge (Cornel & Schaum, 2009). According to the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment in Finland (2020) 4.5 kt P/a is left available in sewage sludge. This final disposal of phosphorus-rich sludge is a P loss considering the phosphorus recovery needs (Xu et al., 2018).

1.2 Phosphorus recovery

Phosphorus recovery refers to the extraction of P from either the water or sludge phase into a separate fraction, separating it from harmful substances and subsequent conversion into a raw material to use in the fertilizer or chemical phosphorus industries (Berninger et al., 2017; Cornel & Schaum, 2009). Phosphate is a highly soluble form of phosphorus and important for understanding total phosphorus leaching (Xu et al., 2015). It is also the form of phosphorus needed for mineral product formation (Zhang et al., 2025). The majority of P contained in municipal wastewater is in dissolved form such as orthophosphate or polyphosphate, while the remainder is bound to organic matter. (Ortho)phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) ions react with water to form hydrogen phosphates. Plants utilize phosphorus as dihydrogen phosphate or hydrogen phosphate ions. This distribution makes 100% recovery in usable form a significant challenge (Berninger et al., 2017).

The efficiency of the P recovery process is determined by phosphorus dissolution potential, which in turn depends on phosphorus speciation (Saoudi et al., 2023). Phosphorus removed by EBPR is generally more easily processed into products compared to chemically precipitated phosphorus. When phosphorus reacts with iron in the wastewater treatment process, it precipitates as iron phosphate compounds (Fe-Ps). Due to high stability and low mobility of such compounds, current chemical recovery technologies require large changes in pressure, temperature, and pH, making recovery only economically viable primarily in WWTPs using EBPR (de-Bashan & Bashan, 2004; Wilfert et al., 2015). Chemical precipitation renders the precipitates difficult and, according to some, even impossible to recycle in an economically feasible industrial manner (de-Bashan & Bashan, 2004).

Several methods to recover phosphorus from sludge and convert it into a safe and reusable form have been developed and deployed at various scales using technologies using chemical, physical, or biological approaches (Wilfert et al., 2015). These technologies can be categorized into three groups: (1) P recovery from solid sewage sludge, (2) recovery from leachates or effluent liquids, and (3) recovery from sewage sludge ash (SSA). The leachate, or effluent, refers to the liquid remaining from the thickening or dewatering of anaerobically digested (AD)

sludge, from which only the dissolved P can be easily recovered by precipitation as phosphoric minerals, ion exchange or adsorption (Mayer et al., 2016; Xu et al., 2018). Thermal treatment methods such as sludge incineration, pyrolysis or hydrothermal carbonization to ash are not widely used in Finland, mainly due to strict authorisation requirements and high energy demands of the process, but have shown large potential, for example, when combined with wet chemical recovery methods (Vilpanen & Seppälä, 2025). Currently, there is no economically viable industrial-scale process to recover phosphorus directly from solid sludge (Cieślik & Konieczka, 2017; de-Bashan & Bashan, 2004; Mayer et al., 2016).

Most of these recovery methods are hindered by inadequate management of waste materials and residues, economical unfeasibility, or are not technically implementable. Furthermore, chemical extraction and hygienization are often required to achieve a clean product, leading to a high chemical consumption and making the implementation of such technologies also a significant financial risk for WWTPs (Cieślik & Konieczka, 2017; de-Bashan & Bashan, 2004; Egle et al., 2015). Additionally, simultaneous recovery of the phosphorus coagulant used in the process would be beneficial to make the process fully circular and conforming to the principles of sustainable development, but also decrease operational and disposal costs, reduce the total sludge volume, and mitigate secondary pollution (Wu et al., 2023).

1.3 Methods of phosphorus recovery from solid sewage sludge

Solid sludge is heterogeneous, semi-solid material in which approximately 90% of the influent phosphorus in wastewater is concentrated. Most of the wastewater sludge consists of organic material. Sludge contains approximately 2–4 % P by dry weight (Aziz & Mustafa, 2022; Berninger et al., 2017). Sludge also contains other nutrients such as nitrogen and potassium, pathogens, heavy metals, such as copper, zinc, and cadmium, microplastics, PAH compounds, and drug residues. Sludge composition can vary according to seasonal influences, treatment procedures applied, and waste sources. The pH of sludge is usually within the range of 6–8, with digested sludge being slightly more alkaline (Aziz & Mustafa,

2022; Urho et al., 2022). Sewage sludge has a slight pH buffering capacity towards pH change (Meng et al., 2022).

Solubilization of the chemically or biologically bound phosphorus is necessary before the recovery process (Egle et al., 2015). Due to the high water and organic matter content, sludge is often treated by anaerobic digestion, composting, dewatering or a combination of different processes in WWTPs prior to its disposal or use, altering the speciation of phosphorus throughout the treatment process (Vilpanen & Seppälä, 2025). Phosphorus species in sewage sludge can be classified into inorganic phosphorus (IP) and organic phosphorus (OP). IP is categorized into apatite phosphorus (AP) and non-apatite inorganic phosphorus (NAIP). NAIP consists of P species combined with oxides and hydroxides of metal ions, like Al and Fe. AP consists of P species mainly associated with Ca. The main phosphorus species in the solid sludge are forms of IP: polyphosphate, pyrophosphates, metaphosphates, and most dominant, reactive orthophosphates. OP comprises of P species from cellular components such as ATP, DNA, RNA, and phospholipids. OP is mainly produced by sludge decomposition and microbial metabolism (Monea et al., 2020; Wei et al., 2025; Xu et al., 2015).

The simplest method of phosphorus recycling would be the direct use of solid sludge as a fertilizer (Cieślik & Konieczka, 2017). In Finland between 2021 and 2023 approximately 50% of treated sludge was used as an organic amendment in agriculture, and 43% in landscaping (Vilpanen & Seppälä, 2025). However, this method is controversial due to the co-precipitation of impurities like heavy metals, organic contaminants, pathogens, and microplastics into the sludge as well as the negative perception of sludge among farmers (Mehta et al., 2015). As a result, strict regulations limit its use (Vilpanen & Seppälä, 2025). Additionally, the transport and management of sludge is also expensive for the treatment plant (Cieślik & Konieczka, 2017). These challenges have led to increasing interest in technologies for advanced sludge treatment and nutrient recovery.

Phosphorus recovery from sewage sludge is versatile and can yield many different high-value products after phosphorus dissolution. Wet-chemical or physical techniques are required to break down the solid sludge and release the bound

phosphorus. Sludge treatment methods such as anaerobic treatment, thermal hydrolysis, (wet) oxidation, metallurgical smelt-gasification, or wet-chemical leaching are necessary to dissolve P (Egle et al., 2015; Sengupta & Pandit, 2011). Currently, the most widely used P recovery technologies involve the direct precipitation of phosphoric minerals, which can be directly used as fertilizers in agriculture (Cieřlik & Konieczka, 2017). However, this approach is currently limited to the liquid fraction of digested sludge, which contains only approximately 5–20% of the total phosphorus in sludge. A significant portion of phosphorus remains bound, for example, in the organic fraction of the solid sludge (Saoudi et al., 2023). Therefore, alternative methods for recovering phosphorus directly from solid sludge without incineration are needed.

1.3.1 Wet-chemical methods of phosphorus recovery

Wet-chemical leaching methods for phosphorus recover from solid sludge involve the extraction of minerals from the solid phase by dissolving them in liquid acid or alkali (Shiba & Ntuli, 2017). These methods have shown high recovery potential and seem to be applicable for chemically treated sludge (Egle et al., 2015). pH is a critical factor influencing P release as chemical reactions related to P speciation transformation, such as sorption–adsorption and precipitation–solubilization, are highly pH dependent (Xu et al., 2015). In wet chemical leaching, the pH of sewage sludge is increased or decreased, so the initially bound phosphorus is dissolved. The efficiency of leaching is primarily determined by the liquid/solid (L/S) ratio, sludge characteristics, pH, and extraction time (Donatello et al., 2010; Semerci et al., 2021).

Acidic conditions cause a reduction of the thickness of the electrostatic double layer and decrease the electrostatic repulsion between particles (Tang & Zhang, 2014). As a result, viscosity decreases and mass transfer increases, leading to the release of P from solid material (Shiba & Ntuli, 2017). Several studies have reported that acidic conditions with $\text{pH} \leq 4$ have been very effective in mobilizing P into solution, giving yields of over 70% (Levlin & Hultman, 2004; Zhu et al., 2023). Donatello et al. (2010) studied phosphorus leaching with acid from SSA and obtained up to 100% recovery. Then again, Seckin et al. (2023) recovered

only 59% of P from municipal digested sludge with acid treatment, and Petzet et al. (2012) and Xu et al. (2015) only approximately 30% from SSA and waste activated sludge (WAS), respectively. One explanation for the inconsistency of P dissolution at low pH could be the variability in phosphorus speciation in differently treated sludges (Saoudi et al., 2023). Some recovery techniques using acidification reaching industrial scale are PHONAX®, Seaborne® and Ecophos® (Desmidt et al., 2014; Egle et al., 2015; Zhu et al., 2023).

A major disadvantage of the acid leaching technique is the simultaneous dissolution of metals and other interfering ions together with phosphorus, which requires additional chemicals or energy to separate the phosphate from these impurities to ensure the purity of recovered product (Sui et al., 2023). Ion exchange or complexation with citric acid have been explored to solve this issue (Egle et al., 2015). Additionally, the acid demand to reach the targeted pH values is high. Minimum phosphorus dissolution of Fe-Ps occurs at pH 4–6, with optimal recovery requiring pH as low as 2–4 (Ehssan, 2012; Sengupta & Pandit, 2011).

It has been shown that acidic leaching using sulphuric acid is the most effective for phosphorus dissolution at pH range of 2–3, where most metals and phosphorus are in their soluble forms. Sulphuric acid is also commonly used in other industrial applications (Antakyali et al., 2013; Monea et al., 2020; Seckin et al., 2023). In both pilots by Antakyali et al. (2013) and Müller et al. (2006), the leaching pH was increased from 2 to 4 due to the leaching of heavy metals, large acid consumption, and sludge dewaterability being negatively impacted.

Alkaline leaching of phosphorus is based on the generation of hydroxides (OH^-) under alkaline conditions, which then react with metals. The degradation of organic matter and microbial cell damage caused by changes in osmotic pressure combined with the sludge surface potential becoming more negative as pH increases over 10, leads to phosphorus desorption and replacement with OH^- through ligand exchange (Monea et al., 2020; Wei et al., 2025). OH^- replaces the PO_4^{3-} in Fe-Ps, forming hydrous ferric oxide products, like $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, which have a lower solubility compared to Fe-Ps (Alnimer et al., 2023a). While Falayi (2019)

reported potassium hydroxide to have been more effective than sodium hydroxide for phosphorus leaching due to its higher alkalinity, most studies on alkaline leaching have used sodium hydroxide as a base. The optimal pH range for phosphorus leaching with sodium hydroxide is reported to be around pH 11–12 (Alnimer et al., 2023b; Monea et al., 2020).

A study by Sano et al. (2012) reported that alkaline extraction of P from raw ferric sludge recovered up to 90% of the phosphorus in the sludge, compared to only 70% recovery from acidic extraction. Alnimer et al. (2023b) found that phosphorus recovery from the inorganic fractions of aerobic ferric sludges was highest at pH 11 (> 90%), while the lowest was at pH 2 with only 23%. Chen et al. (2019) observed a 70% phosphorus release from ferric sludge at pH 11. In Japan, a full-scale plant for alkaline dissolution of phosphorus from sludge ash and its further recovery as calcium hydroxyapatite (HAP) has been put into operation (Nakagawa & Ohta, 2019).

Despite these mainly positive results, there is still debate about the effectiveness of the alkaline method and particularly what are the sludge characteristics most suitable for it. For example, Monea et al. (2020) found that iron-treated digested sludge had 80% phosphorus leaching efficiency at pH 1.5 and only 9% at pH 13, while aluminium-treated sludge reached over 70% leaching efficiency at both high and low pH. A comparison of iron(II) sulphate (FeSO_4)-treated sludge and iron(III) chloride (FeCl_3)-treated synthetic sludge in the same study revealed significant differences in yield, highlighting the further complexity of the process. The main advantage of the alkaline method is its selectivity, as it prevents the dissolution of most contaminants, like heavy metals (Alnimer et al., 2023b; Wilfert et al., 2015). It can also have a smaller chemical demand as digested sludge is naturally slightly alkaline (Aziz & Mustafa, 2022). More extensive research is still needed on different sludge types and the effect of the coagulant chemical to optimize alkaline leaching efficiency.

1.3.2 Anaerobic conditions and iron reduction

Redox manipulation has received a lot of attention as a method for releasing phosphorus from ferric sludges, as the chemistry of phosphorus, iron and sulphur

in wastewaters are highly interconnected (Flores-Alsina et al., 2016). Iron is commonly used as a coagulant for phosphorus precipitation and sulphur influences the speciation and presence of both iron and phosphorus (Dewil et al., 2008; Flores-Alsina et al., 2016). In Finland iron(II) sulphates are the most common coagulant, so there is a significant amount of sulphur in the sludge (Havukainen et al., 2022; Karttunen, 2004).

Iron is a transition metal that can exist in varying oxidation states, with +2 (ferrous) and +3 (ferric) being the most common. Its solubility varies with pH and oxidation-reduction potential. During anaerobic digestion, when reducing conditions prevail, all Fe(III) in Fe-P sludges is likely reduced to Fe(II) by bacteria or chemically by sulphides. The biological reduction of sulphates to sulphides (S^{2-}) in the wastewater is carried out by sulphate reducing bacteria (Alnimer et al., 2023a). This reaction releases phosphate, increasing concentrations of soluble phosphate in wastewater (Barat & van Loosdrecht, 2006). Reprecipitation of phosphate with the produced Fe(II) is likely to occur unless, iron reacts with sulphides to form insoluble iron sulphide compounds ($Fe(II)S_x$), and P is released from Fe-Ps or iron(II) oxide compounds according to reaction 1 (Levlin & Hultman, 2004; Rickard & Luther III, 2007):

This reaction happens due to much lower solubility of FeS compared to Fe-Ps (Flores-Alsina et al., 2016). Performing the reaction in alkaline conditions, iron is more likely to form $Fe(OH)_3$, due to the abundance of OH^- ions in basic conditions, and reprecipitation is likely to be avoided (Wang et al., 2023). Sulphides theoretically react preferably with $Fe(OH)_3$ compounds that do not have phosphate adsorbed (Wilfert, 2018). At pH values around 8, FeS becomes the dominant Fe species, while gaseous H_2S dominates the system at acid pH values and HS^- in alkaline solutions (Rickard & Luther III, 2007). Hu et al. (2019) revealed sulphides produced by sulphur reducing bacteria can mobilize 70% of the phosphorus in AD treated sludge at pH 7–8. However, the cost of the added sulphate, reduced sludge dewaterability, difficulties in re-separating the FeS for iron recover, and lower net release of P compared to other methods present challenges (Alnimer

et al., 2023a; Likosova et al., 2013; Sui et al., 2023). Sui et al. (2023) found that reductive treatment released mostly inorganically bound phosphorus, while release from organically bound phosphorus was only 7%. Since many heavy metals are less soluble at anaerobic conditions and the leaching can be performed at high pH, the dissolution of heavy metals will be lower compared to just acid leaching (Levlin & Hultman, 2004). Combining wet-chemical leaching with redox manipulation could be an interesting option for a more efficient phosphorus leaching.

1.3.3 Precipitation of phosphorus as a mineral

After the phosphorus has been extracted into the supernatant, it must be recovered in some form. Some current technologies utilize ion exchange membranes, resins, photosynthesis, stripping, or a combination of these methods. However, most of these technologies are not yet fully refined, have high regeneration costs, or are not well optimized for large-scale use. Consequently, chemical precipitation is the most widely used technique for phosphorus recovery (Cieřlik & Konieczka, 2017; Ehssan 2012; Zhu et al., 2023).

The dissolved phosphorus is typically reprecipitated as different salts with low water solubility to recover them as products. Most common phosphoric minerals produced in this way are struvite (1) or calcium phosphates (CaPs) like hydroxyapatites (HAP) (2) (Cieřlik & Konieczka, 2017; Deng & Dhar, 2023). Chemical precipitation methods have been developed and applied for P recovery from wastewater effluent but can theoretically be used in combination of phosphorus dissolution from sludge. Which mineral to precipitate depends on the composition of the wastewater (Deng & Dhar, 2023). Precipitation of these compounds is a highly complex process influenced by multiple parameters. Key factors for phosphorus precipitation include the molar ratios of phosphorus and other agents, concentration of other ions, pH, temperature, seeding, presence of suspended solids, chemical oxygen demand content and flow rate (de-Bashan & Bashan, 2004; Egle et al., 2015).

Struvite, or magnesium-ammonium-phosphate (MAP), is a poorly soluble slow-release fertilizer, and is therefore considered an environmentally safe option compared to many other fertilizers. Recovered MAP is recognized as available as

fertilising products on EU markets and has shown higher recovery efficiencies compared to CaPs, along with a higher market price. It also has the advantage of removing excess nitrogen from the sludge. The crystallization of struvite minerals in wastewater has been widely researched for a long time due to the issues their spontaneous crystallization causes in WWTP equipment (Deng & Dhar, 2023; Huygens, 2019). It forms through nucleation and crystallization according to the following Equation 2, where $n = 0, 1$ or 2 depending on pH (Zhang et al., 2023):

The necessary $NH_4^+ : PO_4^{3-} : Mg^{2+}$ ratio for MAP precipitation is 1:1:1 (Cieřlik & Konieczka, 2017). The optimal pH for MAP formation is between 8.5 and 9.5 since phosphorus appears as more plant-available hydrogen phosphate rather than orthophosphate and ammonium doesn't yet start volatilizing into ammonia. The crystallization process is disrupted by ions such as calcium and carbonates, which form compounds more stable than struvite (Deng & Dhar, 2023; Huygens, 2019).

CaPs can also be used as a fertilizer or in other industrial uses, such as biomedicine and cosmetics. CaPs form most optimally when calcium concentrations are high, like in WWTPs that use $CaCl_2$ as a phosphorus coagulant. Some studies suggest that CaP recovery could be possible over a broader pH range, with higher recovery rates than struvite and lower chemical use if additional ammonium or magnesium is needed for struvite formation. HAP with the stoichiometric composition of $Ca_5(PO_4)_3(OH)$ is the most common target form of CaP used in phosphorus recovery. For the precipitation reaction described in Equation 3 to happen, the solution must be supersaturated with calcium and phosphorus. (Deng & Dhar, 2023)

The required Ca:P ratio for HAP precipitation is 1.7:1. Organic matter is one of the main inhibitors of the reaction, as it decreases nucleation through adsorption. The reaction progression to HAP largely depends on the solution's pH, with the optimal pH range being 6.5–9.0 to prevent excessive formation of calcium carbonates at high pH values (Deng & Dhar, 2023; Egle et al., 2015).

1.4 Research rationale

1.4.1 Aims and objectives

The Finnish Ministry of the Environment has launched a nutrient recycling action plan (2019–2030), which seeks to utilize nutrients from wastewater sludge mainly for fertilizer production (Finnish Ministry of the Environment, 2019). Similarly, EU has implemented the new Fertilizing Products Regulation (Regulation 2019/1009) which intends to make the use of fertilizer products from WWTPS easier. There is a pressing need to identify new and more practical solutions that make phosphorus recovery from wastewater sludge feasible for widespread implementation.

The objective of this thesis is to develop an effective and practical method to recover phosphorus from solid wastewater sludge by chemical leaching. Additionally, this thesis aims to better understand the challenges associated with phosphorus recovery from solid sludge by wet-chemical methods and compare leaching efficiency of different sludge materials. This study will investigate phosphorus dissolution across a range of pH values, comparing anaerobically treated sludge samples gathered at different points of the wastewater treatment process. All sludge samples are from a WWTP using iron(II) sulphate (FeSO_4) as a coagulant. Special interest is also given to the comparison of alkaline and acid treatment.

While there is considerable theoretical evidence to support wet-chemical phosphorus extraction methods from the liquid phase, there is still limited research done on the impacts of pH change on phosphorus dissolution from anaerobically digested solid sludge, and sludge treated with FeSO_4 as a coagulant. Positive results have mainly been reported for sludge treated with aluminium (Xu et al., 2018), SSA (Nakagawa & Ohta, 2019) or with sludge treated with EBPR (Semerci

et al., 2021), none of which are methods commonly used in Finland (Berninger et al., 2017; Vilpanen & Seppälä, 2025). Additionally, variations in sludge origin, like differences in its physicochemical characteristics and treatment processes, may influence phosphorus leaching behaviours and recovery yields considerably. Wilfert et al. (2015) theorized that the type of Fe-P mineral could affect phosphorus even more than has been understood. Moreover, chemical consumption has also been observed to vary between sludges even with otherwise the same sludge treatment process (Antakyali et al., 2013; Monea et al., 2020). Therefore, the aim of this study is to get a comprehensive understanding of the potential of wet-chemical leaching in the context of different FeSO_4 -treated sludge materials, to evaluate the applicability of these methods in WWTPs in Finland.

1.4.2 Hypothesis

The main hypothesis of this study is that the pH of the leaching solution significantly affects phosphorus dissolution, with higher phosphorus recovery expected at acidic or alkaline conditions compared to starting pH of the sludge. Furthermore, it is hypothesized that phosphorus recovery through acid leaching will prove to be more effective than alkaline leaching with both digested sludge and non-digested sludge materials.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Samples and materials

This study was conducted at the University of Helsinki Lahti Campus between May 2024 and May 2025. The sludge materials were collected from Lahti Aqua Ltd. Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP, Lahti, Finland) in August 2024. Lahti Aqua employs mechanical, chemical, and biological treatment processes for wastewater treatment (Kaikkonen, 2021). During mechanical treatment, larger particles, grease, and oil are removed from the wastewater. In chemical treatment FeSO_4 is added as a phosphorus coagulant. The resulting sludge undergoes anaerobic digestion followed by a dewatering process to reduce sludge mass, destroy pathogens and generate biogas (Karttunen, 2004).

Four different sludge materials from throughout the sludge treatment process were researched in this thesis: digester feed (DF), digested sludge (Dig S), dewatered sludge (DS) and the liquid from the dewatered sludge (DS liquid). On the collection day, the sludges were weighed for dry weight (DW), fixed solids (FS) and volatile solid (VS) analysis, and pH measurement, and measured into 50 mL or 1.5 mL centrifuge tubes for the elemental analyses. The remaining sludge was then weighed and stored in glass jars. Each 2-L glass jar was filled with 500 g of sludge material, with three jars used per pH unit studied for triplicate measurements. For dewatered sludge, a sludge-to-water ratio of 1:4 was used (125 g sludge: 375 g Milli-Q water). The sludge was continuously mixed to increase homogeneity. All samples were then frozen at -20°C for the leaching experiments done within the following week.

All chemicals used in this study were analytical reagent grade, purchased from Fisher Scientific (Vantaa, Finland) and diluted or dissolved in Milli-Q water (18.2 M Ω cm at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) to required concentrations.

2.2 Physiochemical analyses of the sludge materials

The physiochemical properties of the sludge materials were determined according to standard analytical methods. The DW, FS and VS contents were determined using standardized gravimetric methods in six replicates. Sludge samples were dried in pre-weighed crucibles at 105°C for approximately 16 hours (Memmert UN30, Schwabach, Germany). After drying the samples were weighed to determine the DW. To determine the FS and VS content, the samples were subsequently re-heated at 550°C for 4 hours (Snol 30/1100 Uomega, Utena, Lithuania). After cooling to room temperature of $21 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, the samples were weighed to calculate the FS and VS content.

The initial pH of each sludge material was measured by centrifuging 5 g samples (Heraeus 1S-R, DJB Labcare, Buckinghamshire, UK; 3000 \times g, 10 min). The pH was measured from the samples using InoLab series pH 720 m pH meter (Weilheim, Germany).

2.3 Experimental setup for phosphorus dissolution

Phosphorus leaching experiments consisted of both acid and alkaline treatments of sludge samples, followed by solid-liquid separation and subsequent analysis. The leaching experiment was conducted in room temperature (21 ± 2 °C) as temperature has been shown to have minimal effect on leaching (Sano et al., 2012; Semerci et al., 2021). For this, the frozen jars were slowly thawed in water baths (43 ± 1.5 °C). Acid leaching was conducted using 5.0 M sulphuric acid to lower the pH to 2 and 4. Ammonium hydroxide was tested as it could be potentially recycled from the ammonium stripping process of the wastewater treatment process, making the process more circular. However, ammonium hydroxide couldn't reach pH above 10.5, so leaching experiments were conducted at pH 9.5 and 10.5 using 9.0 M ammonium hydroxide and pH 12 using 6.0 M sodium hydroxide. At pH range of 7–9 there is a risk of phosphorus reprecipitation early (Xu et al., 2015). The pH was monitored throughout the pH adjustment by centrifuging a 5 g sample (Heraeus 1S-R, DJB Labcare, Buckinghamshire, UK), as described earlier.

Following the pH adjustment, the jars were purged with nitrogen gas for few minutes to maintain anaerobic conditions (domnick hunter scientific LCMS30-1, Hertfordshire, UK). The jars were then shaken gently at 50 rpm (Edmund Bühler GmbH SM 30 A, Bodelshausen, Germany) for 150 minutes, as numerous previous studies reported that 120 minutes is the minimum duration required for optimal phosphorus leaching (Seckin et al., 2023; Semerci et al., 2021; Shiba & Ntuli, 2017). After the shaking period, samples were collected into 50 mL centrifuge tubes. The samples were stored at -20 °C for further analyses done within the next two months.

2.4 Chemical analyses

Leached phosphorus was analyzed as a concentration of phosphate in the liquid phase of the sample. Phosphate concentration was determined using an ascorbic

acid method based on APHA (2012). The frozen samples were thawed in a water bath (43 ± 1.5 °C). The liquid phase was separated by centrifugation (Heraeus 1S-R, DJB Labcare, Buckinghamshire, UK; 3000 \times g, 20 min). The pH 2,4, and 12 samples for all sludge materials, as well as the pH 10.5 samples for DS, were diluted to a ratio of 1:1000. The remaining pH 9.5 and 10.5 samples were diluted to a ratio of 1:100, while the samples with the initial pH were diluted to a ratio of 1:10. Eight calibration standards of 0, 2, 10, 50, 100, 250, 500, 1000 μ g P/L were diluted from control solution (1 mg P/L). For the colorimetric analysis, 400 μ l of both ascorbic acid (50 g/L) and molybdate reagent containing 130 g/L of ammonium heptamolybdate, 3500 mg/L of potassium antimony(III)oxotartrate and sulphuric acid (40.6%), were added to the samples. The phosphate concentration of the samples was analyzed using a spectrophotometer at an absorbance of 700 nm, 15–30 min after adding the reagents (Shimadzu UV-2401 PC, Kyoto, Japan).

Phosphorus leaching efficiency was calculated based on the total phosphorus in the sludge acquired from literature. According to Tynnenen (2011), dewatered sludge at Lahti Aqua contains approximately 36.05 mg P/g dry weight. After calculating the leached amount as mg P/g from the FS content of the sludge materials (Table 1), the phosphorous leaching efficiency (%) was calculated according to Equation 4.

$$\text{Leaching efficiency (\%)} = (\text{Leached amount (mg/g)} / \text{Total amount (mg/g)}) \times 100$$

(4)

Sulphate concentration was measured as an indicator of sulphur speciation and to confirm anaerobic conditions, as sulphate is the oxidized form of sulphur. Sulphate concentration of the samples was analysed using a standardized turbidimetric method (APHA, 2012). Due to its high solubility, sulphate is assumed to be mostly in the liquid phase of the samples (Dewil et al., 2008). After thawing the samples into room temperature (21 ± 2 °C) in a water bath (44 ± 1.5 °C), the liquid phase was separated by centrifugation (Heraeus 1S-R, DJB Labcare, Buckinghamshire, UK) at 3000 \times g for 20 min. For DF, Dig S, and DS pH 2 and 4 samples, a dilution of 1:1000 was employed. The DS liquid pH 2 and 4 samples

were diluted at a ratio of 1:400. The DF and DS liquid pH 9.5, 10.5, and 12 samples, along with the Dig S pH 12 and the initial pH sample, and the DS liquid initial pH sample, were diluted at a ratio of 1:10. The DF initial pH sample was diluted to 1:100. The Dig S pH 9.5 and 10.5, as well as the DS pH 9.5, 10.5, 12, and initial pH samples were not diluted. Standards of 0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40 $\mu\text{g SO}_4/\text{L}$ were diluted from standard sulphate solution (100 $\mu\text{g SO}_4/\text{mL}$). A buffer solution contained 30 g/L of magnesium chloride hexahydrate, 5 g/L of sodium acetate trihydrate, 1.0 g/L potassium nitrate, and 20 mL/L acetic acid (99%). For the turbidimetric analysis, 2 mL of the buffer solution was pipetted into the solution, and a volume of 0.02–0.03 mL of barium chloride crystals was added using the tip of a spoon. The samples were mixed using a magnetic stirrer for 60 ± 2 seconds, and analyzed with a spectrophotometer at an absorbance of 420 nm 5 ± 0.5 minutes later (Shimadzu UV-2401 PC, Kyoto, Japan).

Iron(II) sulphate treated digested sludge contains around 15 mg/g DW of sulphur (Havukainen et al., 2022). Sulphate leaching efficiency was calculated from this value by using Equation 4, for information on how large of a portion of the total sulphur in the sludge was leached away as sulphates.

Ammonium is highly soluble, and its presence is important knowledge for understanding struvite formation (Zhang et al., 2023). Ammonium concentrations were measured using the o-phthalic aldehyde fluorescence method adapted from Holmes et al. (1999) by the Helsinki University Environmental Laboratory (Lahti, Finland). The samples were thawed to room temperature (21 ± 2 °C). Standards of 50, 100, 500, 1000 and 2500 $\mu\text{g N/L}$ were diluted from standard ammonia solution (10 mg N/L). A volume of 250 μL of each sample and standard was pipetted into a microtiter plate. A working reagent solution contained 947.9 mL/L of sodium tetraborate buffer (40 g/L), 4.74 mL/L sodium sulfide (8g/L), and 47.39 mL/L OPA solution (40 g/L of ortho-phthalaldehyde diluted to ethanol (99%)). For the analysis, 1000 μL of the working reagent solution is pipetted to each well. The plates were incubated at room temperature (21 ± 2 °C) for 165–210 minutes, protected from light. Fluorescence was measured using a microplate reader at 420 nm (Tecan, Zürich, Switzerland).

2.5 Statistical analyses

The data obtained from the chemical analyses were first organized using Microsoft Excel. Outliers were identified and excluded. The data from each analysis were then processed using IBM SPSS Statistics 28. Levene's test was used as a preliminary test to evaluate the homogeneity of variances. A p-value of 0.001 was significant (≤ 0.05) and indicated that the variances were significantly different and the data are non-parametric (Gastwirth et al., 2009). The Kruskal-Wallis and Mann-Whitney U-tests were conducted to assess statistical differences among pH-values, sludge materials, and their interactions.

3 Results

3.1 Physicochemical analysis and pH results of leaching experiments

In the initial sludges, DS had the highest dry weight of 0.28 g/g DW, while the DS liquid had the lowest dry weight of 0.0016 g/g DW (Table 1). The DW values remained similar before (0.025 g/g DW) and after digestion (0.021 g/g DW). DS liquid had the highest FS content of 0.46 g/g DW, while DF had the lowest of 0.23 g/g DW. Consequently, the VS content remained relatively consistent across all sludge materials, with the highest VS concentration found in the DF (0.77 g/g DW) and the lowest in the DS liquid (0.54 g/g DW).

Table 1. The physicochemical characteristics of the sludge materials presented as average \pm standard deviation on a dry weight (DW) basis. DF, digester feed; Dig S, digested sludge; DS, dewatered digested sludge; DS liquid, liquid of the dewatered sludge; VS, volatile solids; FS, fixed solids.

	DF	Dig S	DS	DS liquid
DW (g/g)	0.025 \pm 0.00016	0.021 \pm 0.0010	0.28 \pm 0.0012	0.0016 \pm 0.00011
VS (g/g)	0.77 \pm 0.0010	0.64 \pm 0.0026	0.63 \pm 0.0018	0.54 \pm 0.033
FS (g/g)	0.23 \pm 0.0011	0.36 \pm 0.0026	0.37 \pm 0.0018	0.46 \pm 0.033

After setting the pH to the desired level, the pH gradually shifted back toward original pH during the 2.5 hour leaching period, with a pH change of approximately one pH unit for DS and around 0.5 units for other sludge materials. Because of this, the actual pH values set during the leaching experiment as well as the starting pH of the sludge materials are listed in Table 2. The starting pH values varied across the sludge materials: DF had a pH of 6.5, Dig S had a pH of 7.2, DS had a pH of 7.8 and DS liquid had a starting pH of 8.0.

Table 2. The aimed pH value and the average \pm standard deviation of pH values set (n=3) in the jars for phosphorus leaching experiment. DF, digester feed; Dig S, digested sludge; DS, dewatered digested sludge; DS liquid, liquid of the dewatered sludge.

pH	DF	Dig S	DS	DS liquid
2	2.0 \pm 0.06	2.2 \pm 0.06	2.3 \pm 0.2	1.9 \pm 0.03
4	4.2 \pm 0.3	3.5 \pm 0.4	4.0 \pm 0.3	3.3 \pm 0.12
Initial	6.5 \pm 0.01	7.2 \pm 0.01	7.8 \pm 0.01	8.0 \pm 0.01
9.5	9.8 \pm 0.05	9.6 \pm 0.08	9.5 \pm 0.03	9.5 \pm 0.02
10.5	10.6 \pm 0.01	10.6 \pm 0.01	10.5 \pm 0.05	10.3 \pm 0.02
12	12.5 \pm 0.01	12.0 \pm 0.03	12.0 \pm 0.1	11.7 \pm 0.02

3.2 Phosphate, sulphate and ammonium

After the leaching experiments at different pH values, phosphate, sulphate, and ammonium concentrations were determined from the liquid phase of the samples.

3.2.1 Phosphate

The highest concentrations of leached phosphate were observed at pH 2 and 12, while the lowest concentrations occurred close to neutral pH values (initial pH, pH 4 and pH 9.5) across all sludge materials (Fig. 1). For DF phosphate leaching efficiency was highest at pH 2 and 12 (143.7–304.0 mg/L, 25.3–53.8%) but it was otherwise low. Dig S achieved its highest leaching efficiency at pH 2 (289.0 mg/L, 39.4 %), with noticeably lower efficiencies at other pH levels. DS reached its maximum leaching efficiency at pH 2 and 12 (1302–285.9 mg/L, 5.1–11.2 %), but in percentages it was less than that of other sludge materials despite the high concentration leached. DS liquid consistently had the lowest phosphate leaching across all pH levels compared to other sludge material (0.9–25.8 mg/L mg/L).

The highest phosphate leaching efficiency for DS liquid was at pH 2 (35.5 %). In comparison to pH 2, pH 4 was insufficient to release more than 21.0 mg/L except for Dig S (134.8 mg/L). Kruskal-Wallis and Mann Whitney's test revealed that the concentrations of NH_4^+ , PO_4^{3-} and SO_4 varied significantly across all sludge materials by pH. The findings are displayed in Figure 1, Figure 2, and Figure 3 for phosphate, sulphate, and ammonium, respectively. There is a considerable standard deviation across all pH levels for all sludge materials. Differences in phosphate concentrations between pH values were generally significant ($p \leq 0.05$), except between pH 9.5 and 4 for DS, and between pH 2 and 4, and pH 4 and 12 for DS liquid.

Figure 1. Concentrations of leached phosphate as mg PO₄/L for digester feed (A), digested sludge (C), dewatered sludge (E) and the liquid from sludge dewatering (G) at different pH values, as well as phosphate leaching efficiency as % of total phosphorus in the sludge for digester feed (B), digested sludge (D), dewatered sludge (F) and the liquid from sludge dewatering (H) at different pH values. The error bars indicate standard deviation (n=3). The letters next to the error bars show statistically significant differences (Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Mann-Whitney's test)

3.2.2 Sulphate

The highest sulphate levels were observed at pH 2 and 4 across all sludge materials (3890–10466 $\mu\text{g/L}$; Fig. 2) due to the use of sulphuric acid in pH adjustment. The sulphate content is consistently lower across all sludge materials at other pH levels ($\leq 86.0 \mu\text{g/L}$), but the sulphate concentration in DF before pH adjustment was noticeably higher than in other samples (223.0 $\mu\text{g/L}$). There is a high degree of variability in sulphate concentrations across all pH levels for all sludge materials, as evidenced by high standard deviations. The differences between pH 9.5 and 10.5, 9.5 and 12 and 10.5 and 12 were only significant for Dig S. The difference between pH 12 and the initial pH was significant for DF, but not for other sludge materials. The differences between 10.5 and the initial pH were significant for DF and DS liquid, but not for Dig S and DS. DS liquid showed no significant difference between 9.5 and the initial pH but it was significant for other materials.

Sulphate leaching efficiency was minimal for all sludge materials, with most not exceeding 0.21 % at pH levels other than 2 and 4 (Fig. 2). The highest sulphate leaching efficiencies were observed at pH 2 and 4, with DS liquid showing the highest (10.6–15.2%) and DS the lowest (0.2–0.3%) yields. The neutral pH levels (initial pH, pH 9.5 and pH 10.5) exhibited the lowest sulphate leaching efficiency (0–0.2%) for all sludge materials.

Figure 2. Concentrations of leached sulphate as $\mu\text{g SO}_4/\text{L}$ for digester feed (A), digested sludge (C), dewatered sludge (E) and the liquid from sludge dewatering (G) at different pH values, as well as sulphate leaching efficiency as % of total sulphur in the sludge for digester feed (B), digested sludge (D), dewatered sludge (F) and the liquid from sludge dewatering (H) at different pH values. The error bars indicate standard deviation (n=3). The letters next to the error bars show statistically significant differences (Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Mann-Whitney's test).

3.2.3 Ammonium

The highest ammonium concentrations were observed at pH 10.5 (3900–7800 mg/L) and 9.5 (775.0–1300 mg/L) for all sludge materials, due to the use of ammonium hydroxide for pH adjustment (Fig. 3). Ammonium concentrations were notably higher in DS liquid compared to other sludge materials (553.3–7800 mg/L). Dig S also exhibited relatively high ammonium concentrations at pH 2 (880.0 mg/L) and 4 (773.3 mg/L). The lowest concentrations were found at pH 12 in Dig S (44.0 mg/L) and DF (101.0 mg/L).

Figure 3 also indicates which pH values had statistically significant differences. There was no significance between pH 2 and the initial pH, and pH 4 and the initial pH for DF, Dig S, and DS liquid. The difference between pH 2 and 4 was not statistically significant for Dig S, DS, and DS liquid. Additionally, pH 2 and 9.5 showed no statistical significance for Dig S. For DS liquid pH 4 and 12, pH 2 and 12, and pH 12 and the initial pH showed no significance, and the only significance was between 9.5 and/or 10.5 and the other pH values.

Figure 3. Concentrations of leached ammonium as mg NH_4 /L for digester feed (A), digested sludge (B), dewatered sludge (C) and the liquid from sludge dewatering (D) at different pH values. The error bars indicate standard deviations (n=3). The letters next to the error bars show statistically significant differences (Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Mann-Whitney's test).

4 Discussion

4.1 Leaching of phosphorus

Comparing the results of the initial pH and other pH values as depicted in Figure 1, it is evident that acid and alkaline treatment of sludge enhances phosphate dissolution across all sludge materials. Statistical analysis indicated that the differences between pH values are mostly significant for all sludge materials. The leached phosphate concentrations ranged from 130–289 mg/L at pH 2 and from 193–304 mg/L at pH 12 for all sludges, with the exception of DS liquid. Phosphorus yields were highest with DF at pH 12 (53.5%) and with Dig S (39.4%) and DS liquid at (35.5%) at pH 2. These findings align with previously published literature where the total P content has been approximately 500–600 mg/L (Seckin et al., 2023; Monea et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2015), although the results remained lower compared to the best results reported (Alnimer et al., 2023b; Bashir et al., 2019; Quist-Jensen et al., 2016).

Phosphorus dissolution rates can be influenced by the presence of various phosphorus compounds with different speciation in differently treated sludge materials (Antakyali et al., 2013). According to Sano et al. (2012), phosphorus in standard sludge exists primarily as OP, whereas Bashir et al. (2019) identified IP as a major P source in sludge due to chemically assisted P removal processes. Monea et al. (2020) emphasized the impact of digestion and chemical treatment on phosphorus leaching. Several studies have demonstrated that most of the phosphorus released by alkaline treatment of sludge originates from OP and NAIP, whereas the phosphorus released in acid treatment is mainly IP, including both NAIP and AP. AP, however, precipitates at high pH levels (Monea et al., 2020; Sano et al., 2012; Semerci et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2018).

It is important to note that the sludge samples were not filtered before analysis, as filtration could trap organic phosphorus, which may have contributed to the discrepancies in leaching results in previous published studies. Phosphorus from NAIP and OP may not pass through filtration as they can be attached to the top layer of the solid sludge material (Kouzi et al., 2020; Monea et al. 2020; Xu et al.,

2015). This choice may have influenced the results in comparison to studies that filtered their samples. It is also possible that despite not filtering our samples, by centrifuging them, a significant portion of phosphorus remained adsorbed in the solid fraction of the sample.

The leached phosphate concentration and leaching efficiency at pH 12 were among the highest for DF (304.0 mg/L, 53.5%) and DS (286 mg/L, 11.2%), while Dig S (193.4 mg/L, 26.4%) and DS liquid (15.8 mg/L, 21.7%) performed worse. Higher P extraction rates were observed in sludges with higher dry solid and VS concentrations (Table 1). The increased phosphorus dissolution through alkaline leaching from DS and DF could be attributed to the solubilization of OP. DS is concentrated material after digestion with a high dry matter content, whereas DF has not yet undergone AD, where most of the organic material is broken down, resulting in a higher OP content left in the DF. The dewatered sludge at Lahti Aqua also retains a significant portion of organic material after digestion (63%). During the pH experiment, the transformation of the solid sludge was evident by a colour change to almost black and disintegration of the sludge structure at pH 12. According to Monea et al. (2020), the low phosphorus yields in iron-rich digested sludges may be attributed to the release of OP hindering the release of chemically bound phosphorus, thereby explaining the lower results of Dig S in alkaline conditions. Conversely, Bashir et al. (2019) reported that the majority of phosphorus released through alkaline leaching originated from the dissolution of NAIP due to the formation of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$. Without comprehensive knowledge of phosphorus speciation in this experiment, the exact release mechanisms can only be speculated.

At pH 2, the highest leached phosphate concentration was achieved with Dig S (289 mg/L, 39.4%). This aligns with the results of Quist-Jensen et al. (2018), who noted that the lower P dissolution from non-digested sludge compared to digested sludge during acidification was related to the higher dry matter content of non-digested sludge and the reduced release of OP in acidic conditions. Acidic conditions favour the release of IP, which explain the lower results of DF and DS at low pH (Monea et al., 2020). Under acidic conditions, AP and NAIP undergo rapid dissolution along with metals. Following anaerobic digestion, organic material has

broken down and the iron binding the P has reduced from Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} , releasing phosphate more efficiently (Wilfert et al., 2015). This also explains why pH 4 already resulted in a significant release of phosphorus in Dig S (Fig. 1), as also described in Baumann (2003). The transformation of solids at pH 2–4 could be observed during the experiment by the sludge becoming more “porridge-like” and the colour of the sludge liquid turning a yellowish orange, as also described by Alnimer et al. (2023b).

From the leaching efficiency of DS, it is evident that although a large concentration was leached at pH 12, a significant portion of available phosphorus remained in the sludge compared to DF and Dig S (285.9 mg/L, 11.2%). The same effect can be seen in Figure 2 with sulphate yields at pH 2 (10465 $\mu\text{g/L}$, 0.3%). It is possible that the leaching efficiency results of DS are generally low due to the 4:1 L/S ratio used in this experiment. According to Semerci et al. (2021) and Donatello et al. (2010) the optimal L/S ratio for dried sludge to achieve maximum P dissolution would be approximately 20 mL/g in acidic conditions and 75 mL/g in alkaline conditions. The high organic matter content in DS and Dig S (Table 1) may have also limited the release of IP, resulting in lower P yields than is theoretically possible (Quist-Jensen et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2015). Sequential washing of the sample with the solvent may solve these issues.

DS liquid exhibited minimal phosphate leaching compared to all other sludge materials across all pH values, as anticipated, since the majority of P should be precipitated into the solid sludge during WWTP processes (Quist-Jensen et al., 2016). Interestingly, DS liquid exhibited one of the highest leaching efficiencies at pH 2 (35.5%) and relatively high leaching efficiency at pH 4 (19.7%) and 12 (21.7%). As shown in Table 1, this is attributed to the DW of DS liquid being only 0.0016 g/g DW, which means that due to the low total P content in DS liquid, the leached yield appears elevated compared to other sludge materials. Most of the P remains absorbed in the solid material during the dewatering process, and only a small amount of soluble phosphorus is left in the liquid. The lower VS content (0.54 g/g VS) compared to other sludge materials also explains the higher leaching efficiencies observed at low pH, as a greater amount of the phosphorus would exist as IP.

In alkaline and calcium-rich conditions, extracted phosphorus can precipitate as insoluble CaPs, resulting in lower P yields (Semerci et al., 2021). For CaPs to form, the solution must be saturated with calcium. Although the concentration of calcium in FeSO₄-treated Finnish dewatered sludge is typically relatively low, it can still contain approximately 24–54 mg Ca/g DW (Urho et al., 2022), which means that a significant portion of P could have reprecipitated as CaPs at pH 9.5 and 10.5. The low phosphate yields observed at pH values between 6 and 10.5 were likely due to the formation of undesirable compounds such as Fe-Ps, struvite, and CaPs at those pH levels. Conversely, high concentrations of organic matter inhibit CaP formation, and the VS concentration of DF, Dig S and DS all exceeded 60% (Table 1). Other anions in the sludge could also cause metal ions to bond with P due to ion exchange competition enhanced by the buffering capacity of the sludge, thereby restraining their dissolution. On the other hand, these coexisting anions may enhance P release (Gao et al., 2025; Meng et al., 2022). At pH 10, P desorption likely occurs through slower diffusion, as OH⁻ ions displace phosphate on hydrous ferric oxide surfaces, resulting in slow phosphorus release. The concentration of OH⁻ ions is much lower at pH 10 compared to pH 12. Furthermore, the positive surface charge of hydrous ferric oxides decreases as the pH increases, leading to an increased P desorption as the electrostatic repulsion between phosphate and the increasingly negative surface charge grows (Alnimer et al., 2023b).

4.2 Behaviour of sulphur

The sulphate content across all sludge materials and pH values was low (Fig. 2), which is in line with previous studies (Amin et al., 2024). The highest sulphate contents were observed at pH 2 and 4 across all sludge materials, due to sulphuric acid added for pH adjustment. Statistical differences in sulphate concentrations were mainly observed between pH of 2, 4, and the initial pH, and other pH values. During AD, microbial activity reduces sulphates to sulphides, leading to the expectation that practically no sulphates would remain in either the liquid or solid phases of Dig S or DS. This is evidenced by the low sulphate leaching

efficiency of these sludges. If minimal sulphate is detected, it can be assumed that the sulphur is primarily in its reduced form as sulphides and bound to iron as FeS and other metal compounds with low solubility in the solid sludge (Dewil et al., 2008). The dark black colour of the sludges at high pH during the experiment is also an indicator of formation of FeS (Suschka & Grübel, 2014). This suggests that nitrogen purging of the jars was enough to ensure anaerobic conditions, but not enough to turn all the added sulphuric acid into sulphides. Sulphate concentration at the initial pH was highest in DF (223.0 µg/L) as it has not undergone AD or pH adjustment. Sulphur compounds should not be transferred into the biogas produced during AD, which means that the highest sulphate concentration should generally be in sludges before digestion (Dewil et al., 2008). Based on this DF should have a higher sulphate concentration compared to other sludge materials, but this is not the case (Fig. 2). Due to the complex matrix of sludge, which includes both anaerobic and aerobic zones, anaerobic conditions may have already developed before AD, or reduction could have occurred through indirect mechanisms such as electron shuffling (Wilfert, 2018). The higher sulphate concentration in DS liquid has been explained by the high solubility of sulphates, leading their high concentration in the liquid phase (Dewil et al., 2008). For this same reason, the solid portion of DS had a smaller sulphate leaching efficiency than DF and Dig S at all pH values (Fig. 2).

The role of FeS formation and reductive conditions on phosphorus release in this experiment is unknown. Reductive treatment and sulphide formation releases mostly IP, which means that it could have a more positive effect in high pH, as alkaline treatment releases mostly only OP and FeS solubility is highest at low pH (Sui et al., 2023; Wilfert, 2018). However, Likosova et al. (2013) suggested that low pH is more effective for sulphide-induced phosphorus release as it better separates colloidal FeS from the liquid phase. The dissolution of FeS is minimal when pH exceeds 8.0, but in strongly acidic conditions with high H⁺ concentrations, FeS may dissolve into Fe²⁺ and sulphides. At low pH sulphide then tends to convert into volatile hydrogen sulphide gases. During the pH adjustment of Dig S, a faint odor of "rotten eggs" was detected at pH 2 and 4, which may suggest the presence of these gases. If anaerobic conditions are not maintained, sulphide can oxidize back to sulphate, which could also be another potential explanation

for the elevated sulphate concentrations at low pH. (Rickard & Luther III, 2007; Wang et al., 2023; Wilfert, 2018)

A different interpretation could be that anaerobic conditions were not achieved despite the nitrogen purging. This would explain why most of the added sulphuric acid did not transform to sulphides at low pH. Another possibility is that the sulphur and/or iron content of the sludge was too low for the reaction. In Wilfert's (2018) study, the initial sulphur content was insufficient for FeS formation, even though the sludge was treated with FeSO₄. It is possible that a similar scenario has happened in this experiment and phosphorus has been released by other mechanisms. It is possible that a higher sulphur/iron dosage could have resulted to an increased phosphate dissolution.

4.3 Ammonium and theoretical MAP formation

The highest concentrations of ammonium were observed at pH 9.5 and 10.5 across all sludge materials, because the pH was adjusted using ammonium hydroxide (Fig. 3). Significant statistical differences were mainly noted between pH 9.5 and 10.5 and other pH values, while minimal statistical differences were detected between pH 2, 4, and the initial pH, as well as pH 12 in DS liquid. The significantly high concentrations of ammonium in DS liquid can be attributed to the AD process. In WWTP systems, ammonium is removed through nitrification and denitrification as nitrogen gas (N₂) (Karttunen, 2004). Prior to AD, most of the remaining nitrogen exists as nitrates, which may explain the comparatively lower ammonium concentrations in DF (Fig. 3). The breakdown of organic matter during AD leads to the release ammonia-nitrogen compounds, which is evidenced by the increased concentrations in Dig S compared to DF (Fig. 3). The ammonia-nitrogen is then concentrated in the liquid phase during sludge dewatering, resulting in concentrations as high as 1000–3000 N-NH₄⁺ mg/L (Suschka & Grübel, 2014). This is considered a disadvantage of the AD process. This ammonium is usually removed from the anaerobic digestion effluent by ammonia stripping (Guštin & Marinšek-Logar, 2011). The slight increase in ammonium concentration in DF and Dig S at pH 2 may be attributed to breakdown of organic material by

sulphuric acid (Fig. 3). The optimal pH for MAP formation is around 8.0–9.0, suggesting that MAP formation may have initiated ammonium precipitation at this pH (Suschka & Grübel, 2014). However, this is not evident in the results of this study due to the addition of ammonium hydroxide. Under acidic conditions, struvite breaks down into amorphous crystals, and at pH levels above 9, struvite begins to dissolve as the increase in H^+ ions leads to the volatilization of ammonium as ammonia (NH_3), resulting in lower ammonium concentrations at pH 12 for all sludge materials (Fig. 3). This is the same reaction ammonia stripping process is based on (Guštin & Marinšek-Logar, 2011).

The results indicate that all sludge materials, besides DS liquid, contain high concentrations of both NH_4^+ and P (Fig. 1; Fig 3.), making precipitation as struvite products most advantageous. Struvite formation occurs through nucleation and crystal growth, influenced by several physical and chemical parameters. The ideal NH_4^+ : PO_4^{3-} : Mg^{2+} molar ratio for struvite formation is approximately 1:1:1 (Zhang et al., 2025). Comparing the values in Figure 1 and Figure 3, ammonium is in excess relative to phosphorus at most pH values, theoretically allowing for the complete precipitation of all phosphate as struvite. Excess ammonium also increases struvite yields by acting as a buffer against the pH decrease caused by the release of H^+ ions in the reaction (2) (Mehta et al., 2015).

The highest leached phosphorus concentrations were observed with Dig S at pH 2, and with DF and DS at pH 12 (> 200 mg/L), making them most suitable for struvite production (Fig. 1). However, DF exhibited low ammonium concentrations at pH 12 (101.0 mg/L), whereas DS had similar NH_4^+ and P concentrations at pH 12 (313.3 mg/L, 285.9 mg/L), and NH_4^+ was in abundance in Dig S at pH 2 (880.0 mg/L). DS liquid had very low P concentrations (Fig. 1), high ammonium concentrations (Fig. 3), and usually has very low magnesium concentrations (Quist-Jensen et al., 2016), making it the least suitable for struvite production among the sludge materials. If phosphorus is leached into the supernatant at low or high pH, pH readjustment is necessary for struvite formation. Lowering the pH for acidification and subsequently raising it is more intensive than adjusting the pH from already basic conditions. The acid method also has the disadvantage of leaching heavy metals and other impurities into the liquid phase, necessitating

the separation of phosphorus and ammonium from the impurities prior to struvite production (Sui et al., 2023).

Magnesium (Mg^{2+}) concentrations in wastewater sludge are typically low, meaning a supplementary addition of magnesium is often needed for struvite formation. This addition can contribute up to 75% of the recovery process cost due to the significantly higher content of P and NH_4^+ in wastewater (Fattah et al., 2022; Peng et al., 2018). Consequently, research is ongoing to identify more cost-effective options for Mg^{2+} supplementation (Fattah et al., 2022). The magnesium concentration in $FeSO_4$ -treated Finnish dewatered sludge is approximately 2.7–4.3 mg/g DW (Urho et al., 2022), which is nearly ten times lower than the concentrations of phosphorus and ammonium leached in this thesis (Fig. 1, Fig. 3). Phosphorus is the limiting factor for the struvite formation reaction; however, it has been demonstrated that an excess of magnesium compared to phosphorus enhances phosphorus recovery and reduces reactions with calcium, thereby increasing the purity of MAP crystals. The economically optimal Mg^{2+} : P ratio is considered to be 1.6:1 (Peng et al., 2018).

The presence of competing ions in the sludge complicates the prediction of the crystallization reaction. The type of sludge used as a source may contain high concentrations of competing ions, depending on WWTP processes (Aziz & Mustafa, 2022). In this context, alkaline leaching is more effective, as it dissolves fewer heavy metals and other impurities than acid leaching, resulting in higher purity products (Alnimer et al., 2023b). As previously mentioned, wastewaters with high calcium concentrations can hinder struvite crystallization, as CaPs have lower solubility compared to struvite. Although calcium is typically used in WWTPs as lime (CaO) to some extent to elevate pH, the use of CaCl as a phosphorus coagulant is infrequent (Karttunen, 2004). Consequently, Finnish sludges generally exhibit relatively low calcium concentrations, meaning that struvite production could be a viable option in Finland (Fattah et al., 2022). However, according to Urho et al. (2022) $FeSO_4$ -treated dewatered sludge in Finland can contain approximately 24–54 mg Ca/g DW, which is comparable to the phosphorus concentration in dewatered sludge at Lahti Aqua (36.05 mg P/g DW) (Tynninen, 2011). Calcium and carbonates interfere with struvite precipitation by extending

crystallization time and occupying the binding site of ammonium. Additionally, magnesium starts to form magnesium hydroxide salts at pH levels above 10.5, which can disrupt struvite formation if the pH is set any higher than is optimal (Zhang et al., 2025). Humic acid and other organic impurities form complexes with Mg^{2+} , PO_4^{3-} , and NH_4^+ (Cieřlik & Konieczka, 2017). The sludge materials of this study, asides from DS liquid, contained a high concentration of organic material or volatile solids (Table 1). Similarly, it is possible that iron compounds prevent struvite formation by forming vivianite first (Wilfert, 2018). These factors should be taken into consideration for the effective optimization of struvite precipitation. Therefore, it is essential to determine the exact contents and characteristics of the sludge.

4.4 Recommendations for future and thoughts on practical implementation

Conducting a proper analysis of various other elements and phosphorus species was beyond of the scope of this thesis. Measuring the oxidation-reduction potential would have been beneficial as well. Such data would have provided more precise results and yielded deeper insights into the transformations of these elements during the WWTP process and throughout our experiment. It is also established that humic substances are in abundance in WWTPs and can significantly influence iron and P speciation, although they were not further considered in this study (Wilfert, 2018). Most previous published literature has primarily focused on phosphorus release, with little to no attention given to the distribution and transformation of different phosphorus forms. A thorough understanding of these mechanisms behind phosphorus release is essential for optimizing conditions for phosphorus recovery.

The high standard deviations and variance observed across all results may be attributed to inherent differences in the sludge characteristics. There can be high variability in the composition of wastewater treated between days and even hours (Aziz & Mustafa, 2022). Furthermore, despite continuous mixing of the sludge samples throughout the study, the rapid settling of the solid material might have led to uneven results.

In an ideal system the iron used as a P coagulant should also be recycled back into the system. In this thesis we focused on phosphorus dissolution, where the optimal method for iron removal would be as FeS and Fe(OH)₃ at high pH. Although P can theoretically be recovered through these methods, currently the iron from FeS can only be recovered by oxidation or electrochemical methods, both of which require large amounts of energy and are therefore still largely unattractive (Chakraborty et al., 2020; Likosova et al., 2013; Wu et al., 2023).

Future research on nutrient recovery technologies is essential to optimize process efficiency and commercial applicability. A profitability assessment is necessary to evaluate the feasibility of large-scale implementation of this method. Economic and legislative realities present currently the greatest constraints to potential solutions (Desmidt et al., 2014; Neczaj & Grosser, 2018). This thesis did not assess chemical consumption, which is highly dependent on the sludge composition, varying significantly among WWTPs (Monea et al., 2020). For example, Meng et al. (2022) reported that sludge treatment, such as thickening, can greatly affect the sludge buffering capacity and therefore acid and base consumption. Production of struvite alone accounts for approximately one-third of the cost of chemical inputs of phosphorus recovery. Currently, the cost of recovering phosphorus from wastewater as struvite exceeds the market price of rock phosphate (Antakyali et al., 2013; Mayer et al., 2016). Although the market value of ammonium hydroxide is higher than that of sodium hydroxide, recycling ammonium from WWTP processes, such as nitrogen stripping, could theoretically reduce some chemical costs in alkaline leaching. Criticism exists also regarding the focus on struvite production, as Latifian et al. (2012) argues that struvite does not work as a sole NPK fertilizer due to its lower N:P ratio compared to crop requirements. If economic incentives are insufficient, environmental benefits and government regulations must drive the progress (Peng et al., 2018). From the perspective of developing countries, increased national support mechanisms are needed for cost-sharing (Mayer et al., 2016). Implementing phosphorus recovery technologies in the majority of WWTPs globally could allow the prices of produced chemical fertilizers to normalize, improve global phosphorus management, and

prevent economic conflicts in the future (Cieřlik & Konieczka 2017; de Boer et al., 2019).

Achieving this requires a broader range of social and ecological expertise than is usually devoted to these topics. A more holistic, systems-level approach is needed in researching P recovery techniques, along with increased collaboration between stakeholders to develop more standardized protocols and research broader impacts beyond subsystem optimization. Emphasis should be on evaluating trade-offs among technologies across different scales, public acceptance, and environmental impacts (Neczaj & Grosser, 2018). A deeper evaluation of potential environmental impacts is needed to better understand the possible effects on gaseous emissions, energy consumption, chemical usage and nutrient release into the environment associated with this method (Amann et al., 2018; Mayer et al., 2016). The integration of new technologies into existing infrastructure and processes is imperative (Neczaj & Grosser, 2018). Currently, phosphorus recovery techniques suited as such to Finnish practices are not yet available. Existing technologies may either limit or facilitate certain options over others, as can the attitudes of stakeholders involved (Berninger et al., 2017). It is necessary to reconceptualize WWTPs as resource recovery refineries rather than merely as cleaning facilities, as part of a broader societal transition towards a bioeconomy.

5 Conclusions

Phosphorus removal from wastewater offers numerous benefits: safeguarding and improving water quality, enhancing the performance of facilities in WWTPs, producing phosphorus products, and advancing circular economy in societies (Mayer et al., 2016). In the context of new, more sustainable, and circular production chains, phosphorus recovery from WWTPs has the potential to replace direct exploitation of phosphorus from the phosphorus ore. According to some estimates, 15–20% of the global demand for phosphorus can be satisfied by recovering phosphorus from sewage sludge (Cieřlik & Konieczka, 2017). Wet-chemical leaching methods are a viable, relatively low-cost and straightforward way to recovering phosphorus from wastewater sludge, liquid, and ash (Egle et al., 2015). However, the current wet-chemical and recrystallization methods still

require further optimization to increase recovery rates and reduce construction and operating costs (Cieřlik & Konieczka, 2017).

This thesis observed that phosphorus release was improved under both under alkaline and acidic conditions, although some differences in sludge materials were noted. pH and digestion are important factors influencing P release, because of sorption-adsorption, precipitation-solubilization and other chemical reactions related to phosphorus, iron and sulphur speciation being pH dependent (Monea et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2015). The efficiency of P leaching with using acid and alkali depends upon several factors, including sludge composition and previous treatment, the type and concentration of the extractant, pH, and leaching time (Saoudi et al., 2023; Semerci et al., 2021). The alkaline method proved more effective for phosphorus leaching in non-digested sludges, such as digester feed (53.8%) and sludges with high DW, like dewatered sludge (11.2%). Under alkaline conditions, the released phosphorus likely originated from NAIP and OP. Conversely the acid method was more effective for digested sludge yielding 39.4% of total phosphorus at pH 2. In acidic conditions, the phosphorus release was enhanced, along with NAIP and AP dissolving more effectively. This theory is supported by previous published research (Chen et al., 2019; Sano et al., 2012; Quist-Jensen et al., 2018). Alkaline treatment enhances sludge biomass hydrolysis, thereby improving anaerobic digestion, making it a highly attractive option for digester feed (Bashir et al., 2019). The lower L/S ratio and consequently higher concentration of phosphorus in dewatered sludge make it an advantageous resource for phosphorus extraction. The results suggest that optimizing the leaching methodology and conditions, such as employing a different L/S ratio or sequential washing, could significantly enhance P leaching potential further in dewatered sludge. For theoretical struvite production, digested sludge or dewatered sludge appear to be ideal due to their high P release at pH 12 and 2 (Fig. 1) and substantial concentrations of ammonium available for the struvite formation at these pH levels (Fig. 3). Despite the high ammonium concentrations, the leached P concentration from dewatering liquid was minimal (0.85–25.8 mg/L) across all pH values, with yields appearing high (0.2–35.5%) only due to the low DW content of the sludge, making it unideal for phosphorus recovery.

Anaerobic conditions may have increased phosphate yields through FeS formation, as indicated by low sulphate leaching efficiencies across all sludge materials (Fig. 2) (Dewil et al., 2008; Wilfert, 2018). Although many signs indicate that iron sulphides were formed, the extent of its impact on phosphorus release remains uncertain.

The limited characterization of phosphorus, iron and sulphur prevents a comprehensive understanding of P behaviour and fate in WWTPs, as well as the design of effective strategies for P mitigation and recovery, necessitating further investigation in future studies. Additionally, the recovery of dominant metals during phosphorus recovery should be considered due to their various applications. An ideal leaching method would be developed to existing the treatment system at the WWTP, achieve high phosphorus recovery rates, be economically viable, and produce a useful product with minimal environmental risks. This thesis contributes to the selection and development of phosphorus recovery methods and leaching conditions for different sludge materials. It also examines potential reasons for the observed discrepancies between acid and alkaline leaching.

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